

ID	Response ID	Q1 Responsibilities	Q2 AI Tool Duration
eb450ccb-3442-4e64-9762-b9f9ee3c1bb	5	Managing teams or delivery processes	1 to 2 years
d348817b-dcb5-4c99-8a3c-4aa5fe1ff028	6	Writing and reviewing code	6 months to 1 year
22517c76-673c-4ca3-b2a0-4e9ead4b750d	7	Writing and reviewing code; Testing and ensuring overall product quality	6 months to 1 year
f898e15-75c7-409a-96e9-12d753a7519a	8	Writing and reviewing code; Reviewing and improving code quality	Less than 6 months
04b04143-51b1-44f6-bc4b-42f67662cae8	9	Reviewing and improving code quality	6 months to 1 year
969449df-0e62-463f-9546-97f6209beeee	10	Writing and reviewing code; Testing and ensuring overall product quality; Reviewing and improving code quality; Leading technical decisions and architecture; Managing teams or delivery processes	Less than 6 months
b3e28efc-1c67-4865-834c-973332178b8b	11	Reviewing and improving code quality; Writing and reviewing code	1 to 2 years
ab60f067-89c9-4e17-bf4a-fb3897b053d	12	Writing and reviewing code; Testing and ensuring overall product quality; Reviewing and improving code quality; Leading technical decisions and architecture; Managing teams or delivery processes	6 months to 1 year
9656b7bd-5793-46b7-86b7-b35b42923d85	14	Writing and reviewing code	1 to 2 years
ac7397ea-2845-42f4-96cc-7b3b7c99528b	15	Leading technical decisions and architecture	1 to 2 years
9296211b-20a7-4d8a-a8d0-cf609fb60dfd	16	Writing and reviewing code	6 months to 1 year
6518e756-93c6-48cd-ac65-a9015d754e8d	17	Testing and ensuring overall product quality	6 months to 1 year
ee916b7e-ffde-44cc-9ea6-749de3933fd	18	Writing and reviewing code; Testing and ensuring overall product quality	Less than 6 months
7e86a960-471e-471d-b4d1-ac7fc00417fe	19	Testing and ensuring overall product quality; Leading technical decisions and architecture; Reviewing and improving code quality	1 to 2 years
b443e70c-a95c-49ef-8d62-685b14cf2099	20	Writing and reviewing code	1 to 2 years
b4b248dd-7bb1-49f9-b0ed-9720c792c32f	21	Writing and reviewing code; Testing and ensuring overall product quality; Reviewing and improving code quality	Less than 6 months
21ac7bc7-3f09-4f12-9a6e-36afe640928	22	Writing and reviewing code	6 months to 1 year
fb50646c-f177-4063-82a2-e3a776b32bdb	23	Reviewing and improving code quality	6 months to 1 year

Q3 AI Tools Used	Q4 Guidance Approach	Q5 AI Maturity	Q6 Challenge Severity	Q7 Top Three Challenges	Q8 Additional Challenges
GitHub Copilot; Microsoft Copilot	Strict governance policy set from above that we are bound by	AI tools are deeply integrated into our daily development workflow	["ct1":3,"ct2":3,"ct3":3,"ct4":3,"ct5":3]	ct5; ct2	
ChatGPT; Claude (Anthropic)	No formal guidance; individual developers decide for themselves	Most team members use AI tools regularly for specific tasks	["ct1":3,"ct2":3,"ct3":3,"ct4":3,"ct5":3]	ct2; ct3; ct5	
GitHub Copilot; Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	We have not adopted AI tools yet or are just starting	["ct1":4,"ct2":3,"ct3":2,"ct4":3,"ct5":2]	ct1; ct4; ct3	
Microsoft Copilot; ChatGPT	No formal guidance; individual developers decide for themselves	A few team members use AI tools occasionally	["ct1":4,"ct2":3,"ct3":4,"ct4":1,"ct5":5]	ct5; ct1; ct4	Noo only them.
GitHub Copilot; ChatGPT; Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist	No formal guidance; individual developers decide for themselves	Most team members use AI tools regularly for specific tasks	["ct2":1]	ct1; ct2; ct5	
GitHub Copilot; ChatGPT; Claude (Anthropic); Microsoft Copilot	No formal guidance; individual developers decide for themselves	We have not adopted AI tools yet or are just starting	["ct1":2,"ct2":1,"ct3":1,"ct4":1,"ct5":1]	ct1; ct2; ct3	
GitHub Copilot; ChatGPT; Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist; Claude (Anthropic); Microsoft Copilot; Mistral AI; Other: Gamma.ai, perplexity.ai	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	Most team members use AI tools regularly for specific tasks	["ct1":4,"ct2":5,"ct3":5,"ct4":4,"ct5":3]	ct2; ct1; ct3	Contextual based analysis must be improved
Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist; GitHub Copilot; Claude (Anthropic); ChatGPT; Microsoft Copilot	Informal team-level norms that we follow but have not documented	A few team members use AI tools occasionally	["ct1":4,"ct2":4,"ct3":4,"ct4":4,"ct5":4]	ct4; ct3; ct5	
GitHub Copilot; ChatGPT; Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist; Claude (Anthropic)	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	Most team members use AI tools regularly for specific tasks	["ct1":3,"ct2":3,"ct3":3,"ct4":3,"ct5":3]	ct1; ct2; ct3	Nothing
GitHub Copilot; ChatGPT; Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist; Claude (Anthropic); Mistral AI; Microsoft Copilot	Informal team-level norms that we follow but have not documented	AI tools are deeply integrated into our daily development workflow	["ct1":3,"ct2":4,"ct3":2,"ct4":4,"ct5":2]	ct4; ct5; ct2	Inaccurate output
GitHub Copilot	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	Most team members use AI tools regularly for specific tasks	["ct1":1,"ct2":1,"ct3":1,"ct4":2]	ct3; ct2; ct1	
Claude (Anthropic)	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	Most team members use AI tools regularly for specific tasks	["ct1":4,"ct2":3,"ct3":4,"ct4":4,"ct5":3]	ct4; ct5; ct3	
ChatGPT; Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	We have not adopted AI tools yet or are just starting	["ct1":1]	ct1	No
GitHub Copilot; ChatGPT; Google Gemini / Gemini Code Assist; Claude (Anthropic)	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	AI tools are deeply integrated into our daily development workflow	["ct1":2,"ct2":3,"ct3":1,"ct4":4,"ct5":1]	ct2; ct4; ct3	Memory inconsistency
ChatGPT; GitHub Copilot; Claude (Anthropic)	Informal team-level norms that we follow but have not documented	A few team members use AI tools occasionally	["ct2":1]	ct4; ct3; ct2	
Claude (Anthropic)	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	A few team members use AI tools occasionally	["ct1":3,"ct2":3,"ct3":1,"ct4":2,"ct5":4]	ct5; ct4; ct1	
Claude (Anthropic)	Informal team-level norms that we follow but have not documented	Most team members use AI tools regularly for specific tasks	["ct1":5,"ct2":5,"ct3":4,"ct4":5,"ct5":4]	ct1; ct2; ct4	
GitHub Copilot; Claude (Anthropic)	Documented team guidelines that we actively follow	A few team members use AI tools occasionally	["ct1":3,"ct2":3,"ct3":1,"ct4":4,"ct5":4]	ct5; ct4; ct1	

Q9 Strategy Effectiveness	Q10 Highest Value Strategy	Q11 Additional Practices	Q12 Challenge Strategy Mapping	Q13 Readiness Dimensions	Q14 Readiness Criteria
["ms1":4,"ms2":4,"ms5":4,"ms4":4,"ms3":4]	MS-8: Multi-Model Cross-Checking		["ct1":["ms3"],"ct2":["ms3"],"ct3":["ms3"],"ct4":["ms3"],"ct5":["ms3"]]	["gov":3,"skills":3,"process":3,"culture":3]	["rc1":3,"rc2":3,"rc3":3,"rc4":3,"rc5":3,"rc6":3]
["ms1":3,"ms2":3,"ms3":3,"ms4":3,"ms5":3]			0	0	0
["ms1":5,"ms2":4,"ms3":4,"ms4":5,"ms5":"not_used"]	MS-1: Structured and Constrained Prompting		["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms5"],"ct3":["ms5"],"ct4":["ms4"],"ct5":["ms5"]]	["gov":4,"skills":5,"process":4,"culture":5]	["rc1":5,"rc2":5,"rc3":4,"rc4":4,"rc5":5,"rc6":4]
["ms1":3,"ms2":3,"ms3":4,"ms4":4,"ms5":5]	MS-3: Security-Specific Review Process	No only that	["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms4"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms5"],"ct5":["ms5"]]	["skills":5,"process":5,"gov":3,"culture":4]	["rc1":4,"rc2":3,"rc3":5,"rc4":3,"rc5":3,"rc6":4]
["ms1":4,"ms2":4,"ms3":5,"ms4":3,"ms5":5]	MS-3: Security-Specific Review Process		["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms3"],"ct3":["ms3"],"ct4":["ms3"],"ct5":["ms4"]]	["gov":3,"skills":4,"process":4,"culture":3]	["rc4":3,"rc1":4,"rc2":3,"rc3":4,"rc5":4,"rc6":3]
["ms1":1,"ms2":1,"ms3":1,"ms4":1,"ms5":1]	MS-1: Structured and Constrained Prompting		["ct1":["ms1"],"ct2":["ms1"],"ct3":["ms1"],"ct4":["ms1"],"ct5":["ms1"]]	["gov":1,"skills":1,"process":2,"culture":1]	["rc1":5,"rc2":5,"rc3":5,"rc4":5,"rc5":5,"rc6":5]
["ms1":5,"ms2":4,"ms3":5,"ms4":5,"ms5":"not_used"]	MS-1: Structured and Constrained Prompting		["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms3"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms4"],"ct5":["ms4"]]	["gov":4,"skills":3,"process":5,"culture":4]	["rc1":3,"rc2":4,"rc3":4,"rc4":5,"rc5":4,"rc6":4]
["ms1":5,"ms2":5,"ms3":5,"ms4":5,"ms5":5]	MS-4: Incremental Generation and Bounded Task Scoping		["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms4"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms4"],"ct5":["ms4"]]	["gov":4,"skills":4,"process":4,"culture":4]	["rc1":4,"rc2":4,"rc3":4,"rc4":4,"rc5":4,"rc6":4]
["ms1":3,"ms2":3,"ms3":3,"ms4":3,"ms5":3]	MS-1: Structured and Constrained Prompting		["ct1":["ms3"],"ct2":["ms3"],"ct3":["ms3"],"ct4":["ms3"],"ct5":["ms3"]]	["gov":3,"skills":3,"process":3,"culture":3]	["rc1":3,"rc2":3,"rc3":3,"rc4":3,"rc5":3,"rc6":3]
["ms1":4,"ms2":4,"ms3":4,"ms5":4,"ms4":3]	MS-5: Multi-Model Cross-Checking	None	["ct1":["ms3"],"ct2":["ms4"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms3"],"ct5":["ms4"]]	["gov":3,"skills":4,"process":3,"culture":4]	["rc1":3,"rc2":4,"rc3":4,"rc4":3,"rc5":4,"rc6":4]
["ms1":2,"ms2":2,"ms3":3,"ms4":3,"ms5":3]	MS-5: Multi-Model Cross-Checking		["ct1":["ms2"],"ct2":["ms1"],"ct3":["ms2"],"ct4":["ms1"],"ct5":["ms2"]]	["gov":2,"skills":1,"process":2,"culture":1]	["rc1":5,"rc2":5,"rc3":5,"rc4":4,"rc5":5,"rc6":5]
["ms1":4,"ms2":4,"ms3":4,"ms4":4,"ms5":4]	MS-4: Incremental Generation and Bounded Task Scoping		["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms4"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms4"],"ct5":["ms4"]]	["gov":5,"skills":4,"process":4,"culture":4]	["rc1":4,"rc2":4,"rc3":4,"rc4":4,"rc5":4,"rc6":4]
["ms1":1,"ms2":2,"ms4":1,"ms3":1,"ms5":2]	MS-3: Security-Specific Review Process	No	["ct1":["ms1"],"ct2":["ms2"],"ct3":["ms1"],"ct4":["ms1"],"ct5":["ms2"]]	["gov":1,"culture":1]	["rc2":1,"rc1":1]
["ms1":1,"ms2":3,"ms3":5,"ms4":"not_used","ms5":2]	MS-5: Multi-Model Cross-Checking		["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms2"],"ms5":["ms1"],"ms4":["ms4"],"ct5":["ms2"],"ms5"]]	["gov":3,"skills":5,"process":2,"culture":5]	["rc1":1,"rc2":5,"rc3":3,"rc5":5,"rc6":1]
["ms2":1,"ms1":2,"ms3":2,"ms4":1]	MS-2: Hybrid Static Analysis Pipeline		["ct2":["ms1"],"ct3":["ms1"],"ct4":["ms1"],"ct5":["ms2"],"ct1":["ms1"]]	["skills":5,"gov":4,"process":4,"culture":5]	["rc1":4,"rc2":3,"rc3":5,"rc4":4,"rc5":5,"rc6":5]
["ms1":5,"ms2":5,"ms3":4,"ms4":5,"ms5":"not_used"]	MS-4: Incremental Generation and Bounded Task Scoping		["ct1":["ms5"],"ct2":["ms3"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms1"],"ms2":["ms2"],"ct5":["ms1"]]	["gov":5,"skills":5,"process":5,"culture":5]	["rc1":4,"rc2":4,"rc3":4,"rc4":5,"rc5":5,"rc6":5]
["ms1":5,"ms2":5,"ms3":5,"ms4":5,"ms5":4]	MS-2: Hybrid Static Analysis Pipeline		["ct1":["ms3"],"ct2":["ms3"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms3"],"ct5":["ms5"]]	["gov":4,"skills":3,"process":5,"culture":4]	["rc1":3,"rc2":4,"rc3":4,"rc4":5,"rc5":4,"rc6":4]
["ms1":5,"ms2":5,"ms3":4,"ms4":5,"ms5":3]	MS-4: Incremental Generation and Bounded Task Scoping		["ct1":["ms4"],"ct2":["ms3"],"ct3":["ms4"],"ct4":["ms1"],"ct5":["ms1"],"ms2"]]	["gov":4,"skills":3,"process":4,"culture":4]	["rc1":4,"rc2":4,"rc3":4,"rc4":5,"rc5":5,"rc6":5]

Q15 Team Readiness	Q16 Additional Readiness Factors	Q17 Rejection Criteria	Q18 Rejection Frequency	Q19 Risk Classification	Q20 Additional Decision Criteria	Q21 Support Usefulness
Ready: documented policy actively followed with clear review processes		{r11-3,r21-3,r31-3,r41-3,r51-3}	{s11-3,s21-3,s31-3,s41-3,s51-3,s61-3}	{t11-3,t21-3,t31-3,t41-3}		{su11-3,su21-3,su31-3,su41-3}
		0	0	0		{su11-3,su21-3,su31-3,su41-3}
Ready: documented policy actively followed with clear review processes		{r11-4,r21-5,r31-4,r41-5,r51-5}	{s11-5,s21-4,s31-4,s41-5,s51-5,s61-4}	{t11-4,t21-5,t31-4,t41-4}		{su11-4,su21-5,su31-4,su41-4}
Partially ready: some informal practices, varies by developer	No	{r21-5,r11-3,r31-3,r41-4,r51-4}	{s11-3,s21-1,s31-5,s41-2,s51-5,s61-4}	{t11-4,t21-5,t31-5,t41-5}	No	{su11-4,su21-4,su31-3,su41-5}
Partially ready: some informal practices, varies by developer		{r31-4,r11-3,r21-2,r41-4,r51-3}	{s11-3,s21-3,s31-4,s41-4,s51-3,s61-4}	{t131-4,t11-2,t121-3,t141-3}		{su11-3,su21-4,su31-3,su41-3}
Not ready: no policy, process, or shared norms in place	Qa	{r11-1,r21-1,r41-1,r31-1,r51-1}	{s11-1,s21-1,s31-1,s41-1,s51-1,s61-1}	{t11-5,t21-5,t31-5,t41-5}	Qa	{su11-5,su21-5,su31-5,su41-5}
Mostly ready: team-level norms exist but are not fully documented		{r11-4,r21-4,r31-5,r41-5,r51-4}	{s11-4,s21-5,s31-5,s41-4,s51-4,s61-4}	{t111-4,t21-3,t131-5,t141-3}		{su11-4,su21-3,su31-4,su41-4}
Mostly ready: team-level norms exist but are not fully documented		{r11-4,r21-4,r31-4,r41-4,r51-4}	{s11-4,s21-4,s31-4,s41-4,s51-4,s61-4}	{t111-4,t21-4,t31-4,t41-4}		{su11-4,su21-4,su31-4,su41-4}
Partially ready: some informal practices, varies by developer		{r11-3,r21-3,r31-3,r41-3,r51-3}	{s11-3,s21-3,s31-3,s41-3,s51-3,s61-3}	{t111-3,t21-3,t31-3,t41-3}		{su11-3,su21-3,su31-3,su41-3}
Mostly ready: team-level norms exist but are not fully documented	NONE	{r11-4,r21-4,r31-4,r41-4,r51-4}	{s11-3,s21-4,s31-3,s41-4,s51-3,s61-4}	{t111-3,t21-4,t31-5,t141-4}	None	{su11-4,su21-5,su31-3,su41-4}
Ready: documented policy actively followed with clear review processes		{r11-2,r21-1,r31-2,r41-1,r51-2}	{s11-2,s21-1,s31-2,s41-1,s51-2,s61-1}	{t111-5,t21-5,t31-5,t41-5}		{su11-1,su21-2,su31-3,su41-3}
Mostly ready: team-level norms exist but are not fully documented		{r31-4,r41-4,r51-5,r21-4,r11-4}	{s11-4,s21-5,s31-5,s41-4,s51-5,s61-4}	{t111-4,t21-5,t31-4,t41-4}		{su11-4,su21-4,su41-4,su31-4}
Partially ready: some informal practices, varies by developer	No	{r11-3,r21-3,r31-3,r41-4,r51-4}	{s11-3,s21-3,s31-3,s41-3,s51-3,s61-3}	{t111-4,t21-4,t31-4,t41-4}	No	{su11-4,su21-4,su31-4,su41-4}
Mostly ready: team-level norms exist but are not fully documented		{r11-3,r31-3,r21-1,r41-4,r51-5}	{s11-5,s21-3,s31-1,s41-4,s51-4,s61-3}	{t111-3,t31-3,t21-4,t41-4}		{su11-5,su21-4,su31-2,su41-1}
Partially ready: some informal practices, varies by developer		{r11-5,r21-4,r31-4,r41-4,r51-5}	{s161-4,s41-5,s31-5,s21-4,s11-4,s51-5}	{t131-4,t21-5,t111-5,t141-5}		{su41-5,su21-4,su11-5,su31-4}
Mostly ready: team-level norms exist but are not fully documented		{r11-1,r21-5,r31-2,r41-4,r51-1}	{s11-2,s21-4,s31-4,s41-3,s51-2,s61-3}	{t111-5,t21-5,t31-4,t41-5}		{su11-4,su21-5,su31-5,su41-4}
Partially ready: some informal practices, varies by developer		{r11-4,r21-4,r31-5,r41-4,r51-4}	{s11-4,s21-4,s31-5,s41-4,s51-2,s61-4}	{t111-4,t21-3,t131-5,t141-3}		{su11-5,su21-5,su31-5,su41-5}
Mostly ready: team-level norms exist but are not fully documented		{r11-1,r21-5,r31-2,r41-4,r51-1}	{s11-2,s21-4,s31-4,s41-3,s51-2,s61-3}	{t111-4,t21-5,t31-4,t41-5}		{su11-5,su41-5,su31-5,su21-5}

Q22 Ideal Support	Submitted At
The best support for teams using AI-generated code is a structured system that ensures quality, context, and accountability. At a high level, it should include: Automated quality checks (testing, linting, CI gates) to catch errors early Human review processes to validate logic and maintainability Strong context integration so AI understands your codebase and architecture Security and compliance guardrails to prevent vulnerabilities Clear usage guidelines and training to standardize how teams use AI tools	2026-05-01T14:20:02.943Z
Na	2026-05-01T14:54:17.676Z
Troubleshooting	2026-05-01T19:19:51.641Z
No	2026-05-02T03:22:46.059Z
Advanced testing and transparency	2026-05-02T05:05:15.821Z
Qa	2026-05-02T06:37:51.628Z
A experienced developer and coder who can review the code once it is generated for authentication and more secure deployment.	2026-05-02T13:05:18.742Z
Security issues	2026-05-03T17:54:57.206Z
Excellent survey	2026-05-03T17:59:29.539Z
The best support for AI-generated code would be an AI that works like a reliable teammate, not just a code generator.	2026-05-03T18:01:23.529Z
.	2026-05-03T18:05:57.727Z
.	2026-05-03T18:08:04.884Z
No	2026-05-03T18:09:39.467Z
1. Don't follow industrial standards while writing the base code 2. Don't try to fix cause and effects when something changed until specially mentioned by user	2026-05-03T18:11:17.697Z
Nothing	2026-05-03T18:27:21.634Z
A standardized framework to review and validate AI-generated code is essential for effective AI integration. Today, teams operate in silos with inconsistent approaches, which limits scalability. Defining a common approach ac	2026-05-03T18:55:03.471Z
na	2026-05-04T18:58:00.619Z
-	2026-05-04T20:16:19.821Z